

THE RISING OF THE INEQUALITY ON THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF PRESCHOOLS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This thesis highlights the shortcomings of the preschool education system in Uzbekistan. At the end of the thesis, it is mentioned about the work being done to eliminate the shortcomings.

Key words: Pre-school education system, inequality, Types of Pre-school organizations, Ministry of Pre-school Education.

Introduction: “The years spent in preschool are frequently considered to as the golden age of creation, a period in which every kid shines with artistry. However, as time goes on, some kind of corruption takes hold, and as a result, most of us eventually develop into people who are artistically stunted.” (Gardner, 1982). Because of the profound impact that it may have on people's lives as well as on society, public education is sometimes referred to as "the Great Equalizer" in the current world. By functioning as a tool for redistribution, it may assist in guaranteeing that economic progress is shared more widely, which in turn can lead to more equitable national economies. It can also contribute to the reduction of severe income inequality and chronic poverty. In this sense, having access to a decent education may be liberating for people, and it can function as a level and equalizer within society, helping to close the gap between the wealthy and the less privileged. On the other hand, the inverse might also be true: an education system that is very uneven can drive a deeper wedge between us. This is since an education system that is already very unbalanced will contribute to the creation of even more unequal societies by further entrenching disparities that were already there and reducing opportunities for upward socioeconomic progress.

Main part: In point of fact, the issue of inequality is present not only in the system of Uzbekistan but also in systems all over the globe. The primary factor contributing to this problem is the influence that the effects of privatizing the education system have had. Specifically, in Uzbekistan, the number of private preschools is growing daily, and the disparity in the quality of education provided by public and private preschools has become abundantly obvious. In developed countries, the likelihood of a kid coming from a poor family attending school is

around seven times lower than the likelihood of a child coming from a rich family attending school. In contrast, only 75 percent of children from the wealthiest households are able to finish their secondary school, whereas 90 percent of students from the poorest homes are able to do so, even in affluent nations.

Source: Data taken from the World Inequality Database on Education (WIDE). See <https://www.education-inequalities.org/>.

Having analyzed these statistics, there is no doubt that it clearly reflects the inequality has been rising as the poorest children are likely to perform at a lower level than wealthier ones. At the current time, there are 18,254 preschool educational organizations operating in the republic, according to the Information Service of the Ministry of Education of Uzbekistan.

In particular,

- Public Preschools - 6,197;
- Preschools on the basis of Family organization - 10,244;
- Preschools on the basis of public-private partnership – 788;
- Preschools in private form – 1,025;

According to the figures that were shown above, it is obvious that around 70 percent of preschools fall into the private preschool category. In fact, this is the primary factor that contributes to creating a disparity in the educational system, since everything, including teachers, technology, facilities, meals, and so on, is much more dominating in Private preschools in comparison to public preschools. Preschools that require their parents to pay any kind of fee, regardless of how nominal, are out of the issue for the poorest families. As an example, in Ghana, children attending low-cost private preschool chains like Omega Schools are

required to pay tuition amounts that are equivalent to forty percent of the yearly income of the typical Ghanaian parent. Only eight percent of students enrolled in secondary private schools in Senegal originate from households with incomes that are lower than the national average. This finding shows that the cost of tuition is out of reach for many families. In order for families to afford these unnecessarily expensive costs, they are compelled to make sacrifices in other areas of their fundamental needs. If parents choose to concentrate their limited resources on some of their children while ignoring others, particularly girls and children with disabilities, this may cause families to become fragmented and ultimately fail.

After looking at all of the relevant elements and facts, we can say that the primary distinction between the public sector and the private sector is - quality. In point of fact, educated, competent, and experienced educators are constantly looking for a position in the private sector, and the primary reason for this is the high earnings that are offered in this industry. In point of fact, there will be no interest in the preschool teaching profession at all if the pay isn't competitive. To this day, a significant number of experienced and well-trained staff members have left the industry as a result of the poor salaries. Because of this, the President of this country issued a decree in March of this year to raise the pay of teachers. According to Agrippina Shin, who serves as Uzbekistan's Minister of Preschool Education, the tariff rates for preschool instructors and Preschool employees have not seen any increases in the last 27 years. In March of 2018, the Ministry of Preschool Education made public for the very first time a plan to boost the base tariff rates for instructors by a percentage equal to thirty percent. Beginning in September of this year, the basic tariff rates for instructors who have completed an advanced degree will be raised by an additional thirty percent.

This is the obvious and common solution to this problem, which has been done by most of the developed countries. Indeed, by giving them only this resolution, there is a minor chance to minimize this issue.

Indeed, personnel solve it entirely. Since the very beginning, the Ministry of Preschool Education (MPE) of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been attempting to find a solution to this issue. The quantity of public preschools, including non-governmental preschools, is expanding in today's society; nevertheless, the quality of these preschools is not sufficient. As a result of the growth of private preschools and preschools run through public-private partnerships, the total number of students attending preschool is steadily on the rise. It should come as no surprise that there is a significant need for staff. In point of fact, "There is no reason to debate about the quality of preschool education if there are no

personnel.” Because of this, the program of retraining and training should be developed. There are a considerable number of educators who do not have a specialization in early childhood education. There are now jobs available for educators at academic lyceums and institutions. They have expertise in teaching, although they did not complete their pre-school education. Retraining classes that encompass all of the techniques, curriculum, language courses, reading, and mathematics should be developed specifically for these individuals. As Feist (2004) considered the following: social-emotional, physics, natural history, language, mathematics, art, and music are incredibly significant. They will be members of an entirely new generation of educators who have received training in subjects such as music, sports, and other professions, and who will be specialists in their respective fields.

Conclusion: To sum up, there is a significant lack of education in the preschool education system in Uzbekistan. But despite this, it can be clearly said that various changes are being made in the system from year to year, even day to day.

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